

Research papers

Electrical cell-to-cell variations within large-scale battery systems — A novel characterization and modeling approach

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ABSTRACT

Digital twins for large-scale and investment-intensive Li-ion battery systems in marine and stationary applications have drawn increasing interest in recent years. Considering electrical cell-to-cell variations (CtCVs) within the underlying battery model of such a digital twin promises various advantages in the fields of model-based optimization and predictive maintenance. However, the existing approaches for both the characterization and modeling of CtCVs are unsuited for large-scale systems consisting of thousands of individual cells. In this context, this paper introduces a holistic tool chain comprising three main elements: First, a non-destructive method for the *in-situ* determination of resistance and capacity distributions within a battery system is presented. The method was evaluated on a commercial battery module for stationary applications consisting of 64 Ah pouch cells in 14s2p configuration. In the second step, the obtained distributions were used to parameterize a state-of-the-art multi-cell battery model, which allows the calculation of the voltage distribution within the system. The validation showed that the resulting model is able to calculate the voltage spread ($V_{\text{cell,max}}(t) - V_{\text{cell,min}}(t)$) with a mean average error of 1.1 mV for a 24 h load profile. In the third step, multivariate statistical analysis was used on the obtained parameters in order to simplify the original model and thereby reducing its computational demands. The simplification approach allows the calculation of envelope voltages curves within which a random cell can be found with a given probability. In comparison to the original model, the simplified model was able to represent the voltage extrema while reducing the computation time by a factor of 27. This renders the simplified model applicable for live digital twin applications for large-scale battery systems.

1. Introduction

Following the ongoing trend towards electrification in the personal transport sector, lithium-ion-based battery systems have also become increasingly relevant in stationary and marine applications in recent years [1–4]. In order to ensure optimal design and operation as well as availability and safety for these investment-intensive assets, so-called digital twins running in parallel to the physical system have drawn the attention of researchers and industry alike [5–9]. Digital twins may include various functionalities such as data handling, state estimation, machine-learning algorithms or programmable application interfaces [8,9]. As their core element, however, almost all digital twins implement a battery model representing the electrical, thermal, aging or inter-domain behavior of the physical system. In this field, single cell models, whose inputs and outputs are scaled according to the actual multi-cell configuration of the physical system, represent

the current state of the art [8,9]. However, this approach simplifies the actual system behavior, since every multi-cell system is inevitably subject to cell-to-cell variations (CtCVs). In operation, these CtCVs lead to deviations of the individual cells' behavior from the average behavior of the system.

Comprehensive reviews of the relevant cell-to-cell variations in the electrical, thermal and aging domain, their inter-domain relationships and consequences on the system behavior have been conducted by various authors [10–14]. Among all potential CtCVs, variations of the cell capacity ΔC and the internal resistance ΔR , caused among others by imperfect manufacturing processes or thermal gradients within the system, have proven to be of particular relevance in the electrical domain. This is due to their severe effects on the distribution of voltage and current as well as temperature, state-of-charge (SoC) and aging progress between the individual cells in the system [15–18]. Considering these

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Nomenclature

List of Symbols

$C, \Delta C, \bar{C}$	Capacity (absolute, delta, mean) (Ah)
c	Parameterization constant for implicit ellipsoid description (-)
h	Hysteresis state variable (-)
I	Current (A)
K	Slope of hysteresis transition ($A s^{-1}$)
n	Number of elements (-)
OCV, \overline{OCV}	Open circuit voltage (absolute, mean) (V)
P	Probability (%)
p	Normalized hysteresis saturation (-)
PA	Position assignment criterion (%)
$Q, \Delta Q$	Electric charge (absolute, delta) (Ah)
$R, \Delta R, \bar{R}$	Resistance (absolute, delta, mean) (Ω)
$SoC, \Delta SoC, \overline{SoC}$	State-of-charge (absolute, delta, mean) (-)
$V, \Delta V, \bar{V}$	Voltage (absolute, delta, mean) (V)
\bar{x}	Normalized parameter deviation vector (-)
ϵ	Model error (V)
κ	Relative standard deviation (%)
$\bar{\mu}$	Normalized mean parameter vector (-)
σ	Standard deviation
Σ	Covariance matrix

Subscripts

abs	Absolute value
cell	Cell-specific value
cha	Obtained in charge direction
dch	Obtained in discharge direction
i	Cell index, value for cell of index i
init	Initial value at beginning of simulation or measurement cycle
meas	Measured values
R	Representative values
S	Max./min. values on surface
sim	Simulated values

Abbreviations

BMS	Battery management system
CC	Constant current
CtCV	Cell-to-cell variation
CV	Constant voltage
ECM	Equivalent circuit model
NMC	Nickel manganese cobalt oxide
OCV	Open circuit voltage
SoC	State-of-charge

variations of resistance and capacity in the modeling stage of a digital twin promises new possibilities in the fields of predictive maintenance and optimized operation but also requires novel approaches towards both system characterization and modeling.

Determining the distribution of capacity and internal resistance within a system and deriving the underlying statistical relations has been the objective of various studies in recent years. Regarding the capacity distribution, cells have been subjected to both constant current (CC) and constant current-constant voltage (CC-CV) experiments [14, 19–22]. The internal resistance of cells has been determined via DC [13, 14, 19, 21, 23, 24] or AC measurements either at a defined frequency

(e.g. 1 kHz) or at the zero-crossing of an electrochemical impedance spectrum [14, 17–19, 21, 22]. The vast majority of the conducted studies has been performed using low-capacity cylindrical cells due to their easy accessibility and high internal resistance [14, 18, 19, 21]. This simplifies the resistance measurement due to the increased dynamic and transient voltage response. In addition, the necessary current levels for testing large-format, high-capacity battery cells often require specialized testing equipment, which is not available in large quantities within most research facilities. Notable exceptions investigating large-format pouch cells can be found among others in Mathew et al. [25] and Barreras et al. [26].

Across almost all publications, the statistical distribution of ΔC and ΔR is considered to be of a Gaussian normal [13, 14, 17, 18] or skewed Weibull [13, 18] type. Within these distributions, the internal resistance is usually showing significantly larger deviations compared to the capacity. Schindler et al. [19] state that this might be partially caused by the cell matching processes of manufacturers using the capacity deviation as a matching criterion [19]. On the other hand, Wildfeuer et al. [27] attribute the effect to superimposed deviations in the ambient conditions during the measurement process [27]. Regarding the statistical correlation between capacity and resistance as well as other parameters such as cell mass, significant relations are also often found, even though results vary strongly between studies [13, 28, 29]. Regardless of the differing cell types, investigated characteristics or measurement approaches, the existing literature has in common that the experiments are almost exclusively conducted from a laboratory perspective. This means that a set of individual cells is either investigated before being assembled to a full system or that a used battery system is disassembled in order to perform measurements on its individual cells after usage. Methods for the *in-situ* characterization of multi-cell systems without preceding disassembly are not commonly available as of now [11].

In addition to the characterization of CtCVs, the modeling and simulation of their effects on the electrical behavior has also been extensively investigated by various research groups. Both cell configurations in series [15, 25, 30, 31] and parallel [17, 21, 32–37] as well as combined configurations [16, 29, 38–43] have been investigated, focusing on the distribution of voltage (series) or current (parallel) as well as the consequent deviations in SoC, temperature and the aging progress. Regarding unbalanced SoCs in series topologies, a special focus was also put on the influence of the applied cell balancing system within the battery management system (BMS). Exemplary studies investigating this topic can be found at Zilberman et al. [15], Shin et al. [29] and Docimo [44].

Most commonly, multi-cell structures comprising cell-to-cell variations are modeled by multiple electrically-coupled single cell models [33, 35, 39]. A notable alternative is presented by so-called mean-difference models as proposed among others by Zheng et al. [45], which calculate the specific influence of the deviation of a given cell characteristic [45]. Regarding the underlying single cell model of such a battery system model, both Doyle-Fuller-Newman approaches [16, 41] as well as single-particle models [31] have been applied. However, the vast majority rely on an equivalent circuit model (ECM) approach due to its high computational performance and easy parameterization [15, 17, 21, 30, 33, 39]. The usual ECM for the investigation of CtCVs comprises an SoC-dependent open circuit voltage (OCV) source and a serial resistor. Additional components such as RC elements or, less-commonly, Warburg or ZARC elements have also been implemented [15, 33, 35].

A common feature of all shown examples is their cell-wise resolution, meaning, that every cell in the physical system is represented by an individual cell or difference model in the simulation model. Therefore, these models usually require an individual set of parameters and in return calculate an individual output (voltage, current, temperature, etc.) for each cell. While this approach yields precise, cell-specific results, it is computationally demanding. This is especially

apparent for large-scale stationary and marine systems consisting of thousands of individual cells. Consequently, system models with cell-specific resolution are not suited for the representation of CtCVs within live digital twins as of now.

Against this background, this work intends to make the following contributions to the state of the art:

- I. A non-destructive characterization process allowing the determination of the capacity and resistance distribution within a multi-cell system in the assembled state.
- II. A battery system model for the calculation of the electrical behavior with cell-wise resolution.
- III. A statistical model simplification process for the model developed in (II), substituting the cell-wise resolution with envelope curves representing statistical confidence intervals. The intention of this step is the reduction of the computational effort while retaining the core information given by the model.

The resulting methods are meant to form a holistic tool chain for the characterization and modeling of large-scale battery systems and therefore enabling their live simulation within a digital twin. In addition, the characterization process might also be applied for other non-destructive investigations such as testing of battery packs or modules for second life applications [10,11,18,46]. Regarding the topology, this work focuses solely on effects in series configurations, since the separate measurement of individual cell currents in parallel strings is usually not available in commercial battery systems as of now. The potential extension of the characterization and modeling process to parallel effects is further discussed in Section 6.

2. Experimental

2.1. Measurement setup and system under investigation

During the experiments, a commercial 14s2p battery module for large-scale stationary applications manufactured by *LG Energy Solution* was used. Its main properties are given in Table 1. With the module consisting of large-scale 64 Ah NMC pouch cells, the named issues coming along with the low dynamic and transient voltage response of such cells can be evaluated. The system allows C-rates up to 2.45C. The C-rate describes the quotient between the applied current and the capacity in Ah. The geometrical arrangement and interconnection of the cells are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, with the cells being split into two sub-modules interconnected by copper bus bars. The cell naming is assigned from the most negative to the most positive electrical potential. During all tests, the module was operated without its attached battery management system. All test procedures were preceded by a CC–CV charging or discharging phase from an initial SoC of 50% following nominal conditions as specified in Table 1.

For measuring the total module voltage and current, a *Scienlab SL/80/100/8BT6C* battery tester was used. The individual cell voltages were measured via a *Scienlab SL/U/MCM16C*, with the measurement tabs being located on the respective cell connectors interconnecting the parallel cell groups. This does not apply for the cell groups 1,

Table 1
Electrical characteristics of the battery system under investigation on cell and module level.

Characteristic	Cell level	Module level
Chemistry	NMC-C	–
Configuration	–	14s2p
Nominal capacity	64 Ah	128 Ah
Voltage range	3–4.2 V	42–58.8 V
Charge/discharge limits		±2.45C
Nominal charge/discharge conditions		0.5C (CC), 0.05C (CV) at 23 ± 4 °C

Fig. 1. Schematic depiction of the battery system under investigation consisting of 28 cells in 14s2p configuration with fourteen cell-specific voltage and temperature measurement points.

7, 8 and 14, where the tab was placed between the copper bus bar and the fastening nut. The electrical measurement setup ensured an accuracy of ±0.1 mV and 0.05% · I ± 20 mA. During all tests, the module was operated in an *ATT DM340T* climate chamber. In order to determine the temperature distribution within the module, fourteen K-type thermocouples with an accuracy of ±1.5 K were placed between the two cells of each parallel cell group (see Fig. 2). This setup allowed the distinction of electrical and thermal influences on the system behavior. To insert the temperature sensors, the module housing was opened and closed in a non-destructive manner with the cell-stack remaining unaltered. Regarding solely the electrical measurements, the entire characterization can be conducted without opening the module. The thermocouples were integrated via two *PEAK Systems MU-Thermocouple1* CAN modules leading to a total guaranteed accuracy of ±2.3 K. Comparison to a *Lufft XP100* reference sensor resulted in effective deviations of up to 1.1 K.

Fig. 2. Side view of the battery system under investigation. Temperature sensors are placed in between the cells of every parallel cell group and on the outside of the module housing. Opened side panel was reinstalled after installation of the sensors.

2.2. OCV determination

To determine the OCV curve, a relaxation test with a grid of 34 unevenly-spaced SoCs and a four-hour relaxation period each was performed. Charging and discharging towards the grid points was done according to the nominal conditions. Fig. 3 shows the resulting OCV and differential OCV curve after interpolation of the mean cell voltage via the *pchip*-algorithm [47,48]. By averaging over the voltage curves of all fourteen parallel cell groups, the influence of deviations in the initial state-of-charge $\Delta SoC_{init,i}$ and the cell capacity ΔC_i was smoothed out. However, the OCV curve itself might also be considered to vary between the individual cells. In order to quantify this as a potential cell-to-cell variation, the cell-specific voltage curves $OCV_{cell,i}$ generated during the OCV test were fitted to the mean curve OCV by minimizing Eq. (1) using *Matlab*'s *lsqnonlin*-algorithm with ΔC_i as a free parameter [49,50]. The SoC was calculated via Eq. (2) with the distribution of the initial state-of-charge $\Delta SoC_{init,i}$ being obtained via linear interpolation of the initial cell voltages on the mean OCV curve [8].

$$\min |(\overline{OCV}(\overline{SoC}) - OCV_{cell,i}(SoC_i))| \forall \overline{SoC} \quad (1)$$

$$SoC_i(t) = \Delta SoC_{init,i} + \frac{\int I(t) dt}{\bar{C} + \Delta C_i} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4 shows the individual OCV and differential OCV curves after fitting to the mean OCV curve, indicating a visible remaining deviation especially notable at the distinct peak around 60% SoC. Similar deviations were also visible while separately fitting the charge and discharge relaxation curves to their respective mean curve. While a certain degree of remaining deviation might be attributed to the fitting process, a relevant difference between the actual OCV curves in the sense of a cell-to-cell variation seems very likely. Applying methods of the differential voltage analysis as shown among others by Keil et al. [51], the distinct peaks in the differential OCV can be linked to partial electrode capacities. In this context, the range between 0% and 60% SoC is usually attributed to the anode capacity, indicating that the actual amount of active anode material varies between the individual cells in the module.

During the OCV measurement, a maximum hysteresis of 24 mV between the relaxation curves in charging and discharging direction was identified. For further analysis of the hysteresis behavior, an additional step-wise relaxation procedure at a single operational point

Fig. 3. OCV and differential OCV curve obtained via relaxation measurements in charging and discharging direction at 34 grid points. Both curves were interpolated with the *pchip*-algorithm.

(50% SoC) was conducted (see Fig. 5). During this test, the battery was incrementally charged and discharged by $\pm 20\%$ SoC followed by a control loop recharging back to the initial 50%. All charging and discharging was performed applying nominal conditions. The acquired information was used later in study to investigate the influence of the hysteresis on the system model quality.

2.3. Capacity determination

In order to determine the individual capacity deviation ΔC_i for every parallel cell group i , a novel test and analysis procedure based on the standard CC–CV test was applied. The measurement was performed following the nominal conditions. After both the charging and discharging phase, an additional 12-h relaxation phase was added to the standard CC–CV test. After this waiting period, full relaxation was approximated, rendering the measured cell voltages approximately equal to the cells OCVs. By using the obtained mean charge and discharge OCV curve, a corresponding SoC distribution after both charging and discharging was determined via linear inter- and extrapolation. The resulting SoCs after charging and discharging $SoC_{cha,i}$ and $SoC_{dch,i}$ were then used to calculate the cell-specific capacities C_i by comparison to the mean capacity \bar{C} according to Eq. (3):

$$C_i = \frac{\bar{C}}{(SoC_{cha,i} - SoC_{dch,i})} \quad (3)$$

The resulting distribution ΔC_{rel} relative to the mean capacity is shown in Fig. 4. In addition to the 12-h relaxation phase, a 1- and 4-h period was also emulated. The corresponding standard deviations σ_C and the relative standard deviations κ_C are given in Table 2. It can be seen that while consistent in trend, the capacity distribution does change severely within the first four hours, which corresponds to the ongoing relaxation process. In contrast, between four and twelve hours, the difference is minor, suggesting that a four hour relaxation phase might be sufficient for accurate results when applying the extended relaxation method.

In addition to the described process, the capacity distribution can also be obtained as a result of the OCV fitting procedure introduced in Section 2.2. As shown in Fig. 6 and Table 2, the acquired capacity distribution shows slightly increased variations compared to the extended relaxation test results. This might be due to the OCV fitting procedure, which minimizes the difference between the individual OCV curves. It

Fig. 4. Distribution of the cell-specific OCV and differential OCV curves after fitting to the mean OCV curve. The results show a significant deviation indicating varying anode capacities between the individual cells.

Fig. 5. Hysteresis loop test at 50% SoC with $\pm 20\%$ SoC amplitude and control loop in charge and discharge direction.

is conceivable that during optimization, some deviations in the cell-specific OCV curves are corrected by increased capacity deviations even though they might actually origin from variations in the OCV. In order to conclusively answer this question, further investigations on the OCV curve as a cell-to-cell variation are necessary but out of the scope of this study.

2.4. Impedance determination

For the characterization of the transient and dynamic voltage responses, $\pm 0.5C$ pulses at four temperatures (20, 25, 30, 35 °C) and eleven SoCs (5, 10, 20...90, 95%) have been measured. The pulse duration was set to 18 s followed by ten minutes of relaxation and a SoC re-calibration. In the first step, the obtained measurement data was used to parameterize a SoC- and temperature-dependent ECM consisting of two RC elements and a serial resistor. For this process, the pulse responses of the fourteen cell groups were averaged for every operating point resulting in the mean impedance parameterization given in Appendix.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the relative capacity deviations obtained via extended relaxation capacity tests and cell-specific OCV curve fitting.

Fig. 7. Cell-specific pulse responses averaged over four temperatures and eleven SoCs. The elevated curves indicate different variations regarding the dynamic and transient voltage components. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

In addition to the mean parameters, the distribution of impedances was also investigated. For this purpose each individual cell voltage response was averaged over all operating points resulting in a cell-specific mean pulse response shown in Fig. 7. As the results show, the variation occurs both in the dynamic and the transient components of the pulse responses. It is especially noteworthy that the position of individual cells within the set of voltage responses can change over the pulse duration as indicated among others by cells 3 (light blue) and 5 (red). Normalizing the voltage responses by the applied current allows the calculation of a DC resistance distribution. This process was performed directly after the current step as well as after two, ten and 16 s of pulse time (red dashed lines). The corresponding average values μ_R , standard deviations σ_R and relative standard deviations κ_R are given in Table 2 with the absolute resistance deviations ΔR_{abs} being shown in Fig. 8.

As indicated by the bar plot, a significant share of the total DC resistance deviation occurs immediately at the beginning of the pulse (ΔR_{dyn}). This dynamic component is especially pronounced for cells 1, 7, 8 and 14, which relates to the position of the measurement tab. For this cells, the cell voltage is superimposed by the voltage drop over the copper bus bar. With progressing pulse duration, the additional transient components are added onto the initial deviation. While both decreasing and increasing deviations over pulse time might be observed, it can generally be said that the deviation converges after the first ten seconds. This implies that the components, which are affected by the CtCVs, are of comparably short time constants within the range of a few seconds.

Since the internal resistance itself is considered highly dependent on the cells temperature and SoC, it must be discussed whether variations of temperature or SoC within the module overlay the actual resistance deviation during the measurement. Regarding the temperature, a maximum deviation of 0.7 K between the sensors was measured during the pulse tests. The occurring SoC deviation is obtained by interpolating the cell voltages directly before the charging pulse of every SoC step via the mean OCV curve. By using this procedure, a maximum deviation of 0.6% SoC during the pulse tests was determined. A general quantification of the influence of these effects on the resistance distribution is difficult, as both influences are highly non-linear. However, taking the generated temperature- and SoC-dependent parameter tables into account, it can be assumed that a superimposed effect within the low single-digit $\mu\Omega$ -range might well be possible.

Fig. 8. Absolute DC resistance distribution after quasi-zero, two, ten and 16 s pulse time. Resistances of cells 1, 7, 8 and 14 are superimposed by copper bar resistance.

3. Battery modeling

The equivalent circuit at cell level used during the investigations comprises of a SoC-dependent voltage source representing the OCV and a temperature- and SoC-dependent $R_s + 2 RC$ impedance string. In addition, a simple zeroth-order hysteresis model was integrated, using a state variable h with saturation limits at 0 and 1, which determines the relation between the charge curve OCV_{cha} and the discharge curve OCV_{dch} according to Eq. (4). The state variable h itself follows a linear charge counter with the parameter K indicating the slope of the transition between the charging and discharging curve (Eq. (5)) [52]. The parameter K was determined via linear regression of the single point hysteresis loops shown in Fig. 5. The initial transition state h_{init} was set to zero for the following validation, since every initial SoC was approached via a sufficiently long nominal discharge phase.

$$OCV(SoC, h) = h \cdot OCV_{cha}(SoC) + (1 - h) \cdot OCV_{dch}(SoC) \quad (4)$$

$$h = h_{init} + K \int p \cdot I(t) dt \quad p = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } 0 \leq h \leq 1 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

At module level, the model consists of 28 instances of the cell model interconnected according to the 14s2p configuration. Each cell is parameterized with its individual capacity and resistance deviation, initial SoC and, for certain validation scenarios, individual OCV curve as determined in Section 2.2. The resistance deviation was implemented as an offset superimposed to the serial resistor. This implementation assumes that the resistance deviation is purely dynamic and does not change over the pulse duration. As shown in Section 2.4, this does

Table 2
Results of the determination of capacity and resistance variations obtained by different procedures.

Characteristic	μ_C in Ah	σ_C in Ah	κ_C in %
C_{12h}	127.815	0.50	0.39
C_{4h}	–	0.48	0.38
C_{1h}	–	0.57	0.45
C_{OCVfit}	–	0.71	0.55
	μ_R in mΩ	σ_R in μΩ	κ_R in %
R_{dyn}	0.56	17.7	3.13
R_{2s}	0.67	17.7	2.65
R_{10s}	0.85	18.7	2.20
R_{16s}	0.94	19.4	2.05

not fully represent the observed behavior, which shows a significant transient variation. In order to fully model this behavior, cell-individual parameter maps for all five impedance parameters would be necessary. However, since the resistance deviations show a converging behavior within the first few seconds, the effect on the model quality can be considered minor.

In order to reproduce the effects of the occurring thermal gradients within the system, the measured temperature distributions obtained during the validation tests were also implemented as a given input to the model. A thermal sub-model, which would be required to calculate such a distribution was, while available, explicitly left out in this study for the sake of delimitation. Interested readers may refer to [53] for further information. The entire model was implemented in the *Modelica* modeling language i.e. its open-source distribution *OpenModelica*.

4. System model validation

The validation of the battery system model was primarily conducted using a 24-h load profile representing a grid service application for stationary battery system [54]. The load profile was scaled to module-level and covers a SoC range of 5–95%. In addition, a 200-min synthetic battery load profile for hybrid cruise ships with a SoC range of 24–88% was used to cover the marine application. During the validation, three model variants were tested:

- I. **Standard model:** Uniform OCV curve for all cells, enabled hysteresis sub-model, red line in Fig. 10.
- II. **No hysteresis:** Uniform OCV curve for all cells, disabled hysteresis sub-model, light blue line in Fig. 10.
- III. **Variable OCVs:** Cell-specific OCV curves as given in Section 2.2, enabled hysteresis sub-model, yellow line in Fig. 10.

The validation results for the stationary profile are shown in Fig. 10. Fig. 9 shows the measured temperatures within the module as well as the housing and ambient temperature during the test. The key quality criteria (mean absolute error ϵ_{MAE} , maximum absolute error $\epsilon_{abs,max}$ and root-mean-square error ϵ_{RMSE}) for both profiles are given in Table 3.

In the first step, the simulation of the module voltage is analyzed. The standard model (I) achieves a mean absolute error ϵ_{MAE} of 81.5 mV or 5.8 mV per cell. Larger errors mainly occur at low or high SoCs, although the general error pattern does not show any strong outliers. These results significantly deteriorate when the hysteresis model is not implemented (model variant II), increasing the model error to an average of 17.4 mV per cell. This is especially evident at higher SoCs. Implementing cell-individual OCV curves does not affect the results for the module voltage significantly. Regarding the results for the marine

Fig. 9. Temperature measurement during validation with stationary load profile. The chart includes the individual sensor temperatures, the average sensor temperature, the ambient and the housing temperature.

Fig. 10. Validation results applying a 24-h stationary load profile for three system model variants. **Top Left:** Simulated and measured module voltage. **Bottom Left:** Model error on module level. **Top Right:** Simulated and measured cell voltage spread. **Bottom Right:** Cell voltage spread model error. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

profile, generally similar characteristics can be observed even though the impact of the hysteresis model is far less pronounced.

In order to evaluate the model quality regarding the representation of the cell voltage distribution, the cell voltage spread was introduced as a new criterion. The voltage spread ΔV describes the difference between the maximum and minimum cell voltage $V_{\text{cell,max}}(t) - V_{\text{cell,min}}(t)$ over the course of the profile. On average, the standard system model (I) calculates the voltage spread with an absolute error of 1.1 mV. However, the model error proves to be highly dependent on the state-of-charge. While achieving good results with relative deviations below 5% at SoCs exceeding approx. 20%, the model quality significantly decreases below this threshold. This effect corresponds to the increasingly steep OCV curve as well as the increased internal resistances at low SoCs. In addition, a sudden decrease of model quality around operating points of 60% SoC both in charging and discharging direction is evident. This effect can be explained by looking at Fig. 4. Due to both the occurring SoC spread and the actual remaining variation in the OCV curves at around 60% SoC, the voltage spread increases immediately when traveling through the peak in the differential OCV. This explanation is further supported by the results for the model variant III implementing cell-specific OCV curves (yellow line). Applying this model variant, the sudden increase of the voltage spread can be represented significantly better, even though the model clearly overestimates the effect. This overestimation is assumed to be due to the low resolution of the OCV curve showing barely a few samples over the complete local peak. Also, the process of fitting used to obtain the single-cell OCV curves might well be prone to errors, possibly retaining a certain degree of variance which is not attributed to the actual OCV distribution but to deviations of ΔC and ΔSoC_{init} .

In addition to predicting the extent of the voltage spread, it might also be of interest to know, which cell in the system carries the respective minimum or maximum voltage. In order to evaluate the ability of the model to correctly assign the voltage extrema to the correct

cells, the position assignment criterion $PA_{\text{max,min}}$ was introduced. It describes the share of profile time in percent, during which the index of the cell with the minimum/maximum cell voltage in measurement and simulation coincides. For the standard model variant (I) with the stationary profile, the indices for both the min. and max. voltage coincide for approximately 70% of the profile (see Table 3). Incorrect assignments mostly happen at times with insufficient representation of the voltage spread itself. It must be said, however, that the voltage measurement shows a significant signal noise leading to frequently overlapping curves of cell voltages in close proximity. Therefore, the $PA_{\text{max,min,3}}$ criterion was introduced. It describes the share of profile time in percent, during which one of the indices of the top/bottom three cell voltage curves in measurement matches the simulation. Applying this criterion, 87.1% (max. voltage) and 80.8% (min. voltage) of the profile time, a correct assignment was possible.

While disabling the hysteresis sub-model does not significantly affect the PA -criterion, including cell-specific OCVs is clearly beneficial for the correct assignment. This coincides with the expectations, as the effect visibly overshadows the effects of capacity and resistance deviations around the 60% SoC mark. Investigating the marine load profile confirms the results mentioned above while showing in general a slightly lower assignment accuracy. This also reflects the increased voltage spread error for this profile.

5. Statistical model simplification

Simulating the stationary load profile with the described system model requires 86.6 s per hour profile-time on a performant office PC. While this is acceptable for a single module, scaling the model to large-scale systems consisting of thousands of individual cells renders its application unfeasible. Therefore, an approach for the simplification of the system model is introduced in the following. The aim of this

Table 3

Validation results applying a 24-h stationary and a 200-min marine load profile. Results for system model variant II (no hysteresis sub-model) and III (cell-specific OCV curves) are given separately.

Stationary profile	ϵ_{MAE} in mV	$\epsilon_{abs,max}$ in mV	ϵ_{RMSE} in mV	PA_{max}	$PA_{max,3}$	PA_{min}	$PA_{min,3}$
Module voltage	81.5	363.1	102.3	–	–	–	–
- without hysteresis	243.5	655.5	297.7	–	–	–	–
- with variable OCVs	81.5	364.2	102.4	–	–	–	–
Cell voltage spread	1.1	10.0	1.8	73.0	87.1	70.1	80.8
- without hysteresis	2.1	36.7	4.1	78.2	89.5	67.1	81.3
- with variable OCVs	1.0	17.0	1.8	76.6	91.6	76.1	91.4
Marine profile							
Module voltage	103.5	363.3	130.7	–	–	–	–
- without hysteresis	105.5	442.8	138.2	–	–	–	–
- with variable OCVs	103.6	363.6	130.8	–	–	–	–
Cell voltage spread	1.8	17.9	3.4	58.7	98.4	60.1	85.5
- without hysteresis	2.0	19.4	3.9	56.6	97.1	57.4	83.7
- with variable OCVs	2.2	12.4	3.2	68.1	94.1	59.3	91.1

approach is the replacement of the individual cell voltages with envelope curves within which the individual cell voltages can be found with a defined probability. By using a defined number of cells instead of simulating all cells in the system, a significant decreased computation time can be expected.

5.1. Parameter analysis

At the beginning of the simplification process, a statistical analysis of the parameter distributions obtained in Section 2 is necessary. In the following, the statistical distributions of ΔC , ΔR and ΔSoC_{init} are analyzed. Considering the ΔSoC_{init} as a statistical parameter may seem unusual, since it is not a cell characteristic but an operating value influenced by external factors such as the balancing system. Nevertheless, within the tolerance of the applied balancing algorithm, a statistical distribution must still be expected. In the following, the cell-specific ΔSoC_{init} was obtained by interpolating the mean OCV curve with the measured cell voltages just before the start of the stationary validation profile. In the practical application, one would of course rather use the information provided by the management system as an input signal instead.

All three parameters were assumed to follow a Gaussian normal distribution. To test this assumption, the Shapiro–Wilk test for normality with a significance limit (p -value) of 0.05 was performed. The resulting p -values were calculated to 0.83, 0.21 and 0.68 for the three parameter distributions [55,56]. Since all values surpassed the significance limit, the assumption was considered valid. Plotting the three parameters for each of the fourteen cells results in the three-dimensional parameter distribution shown in Fig. 11. With all three parameters being considered normally distributed, the fourteen measured cells form a sample of an underlying multivariate normal distribution.

Investigating the probability density of such a multivariate normal distribution, surfaces of equal probability density are found to form ellipsoids according to Eq. (6). The parameter vector \vec{x} contains a set of the three parameters lying on the surface of the ellipsoid. The mean vector $\vec{\mu}$ contains the mean values for all three parameters and is considered to be [0;0;0], since all distributions were normalized. Σ is the covariance matrix of the distribution and c is the parameterization constant determining the size of the ellipsoid. [57]

$$(\vec{x} - \vec{\mu})^T \cdot \Sigma^{-1} \cdot (\vec{x} - \vec{\mu}) = c^2 \quad (6)$$

The total probability P_S enclosed by a given surface can be obtained via integration of the multivariate probability density function as given among others by Mardia et al. [57]. Alternatively, the numerical integration of all probability densities within a given volume in the three-dimensional space also results in the total probability enclosed by the surface of this volume. With the surfaces of equal density being ellipsoids, it can also be stated that the smallest possible volume enclosing a given probability is also ellipsoidal. In reverse, finding the

parameterization constant c for a given probability can also be achieved via optimization with c as the single degree of freedom. Fig. 11 shows the corresponding surface for a P_S of 80% for the given distribution as well as the respective sectional views for the probabilities 70, 80, 90 and 95%. All contours and surfaces were sampled with a resolution of 0.02%.

While the formula given in Eq. (6) is limited to normally distributed systems, the general concept is also applicable to multivariate Weibull distributions. For this type of distribution, the points of equal density do not necessarily form ellipsoids, which renders the analytical solution far more difficult [58,59]. Furthermore, it must be said that deriving the covariance on the basis of 14 cells does not guarantee a high level of certainty. However, this does not hinder the development and validation of the simplification process, which can then be transferred to larger systems.

5.2. Model simplification

The process introduced in Section 5.1 allows the determination of volumes within which a cell or parameter pairing with its three parameters can be found with a defined probability. If subjected to an electrical load, every parameter pairing enclosed by the surface of this volume results in a defined voltage deviation. Therefore, the entire parameter distribution causes a corresponding distribution of voltage deviations. It must be stated, that normally-distributed parameters do not necessarily cause normally-distributed voltage deviations. The relation between parameter deviations and voltage deviations is given by the model we want to simplify. In the case of this study, Eq. (7) describes how deviations of the initial state-of-charge ΔSoC_{init} and deviations of the capacity ΔC result in deviations of the current state-of-charge ΔSoC in dependence of a given mean state-of-charge \overline{SoC} :

$$\Delta SoC(\overline{SoC}) = \Delta SoC_{init} + (\overline{SoC} - \overline{SoC}_{init}) \cdot \frac{-\Delta C}{\overline{C} + \Delta C} \quad (7)$$

The influence of the resistance deviation ΔR and the SoC deviation ΔSoC is consequently given by Eq. (8) in dependence of the applied current I . The resulting voltage deviation ΔV depends on all three parameters discussed in Section 5.1.

$$\Delta V = OCV(\overline{SoC}) - OCV(\overline{SoC}) + \Delta R_{abs} \cdot I \quad (8)$$

Together, Eqs. (7) and (8) formalize the relation between parameter distributions and resulting voltage distributions. Applying a given load profile and a given parameter distribution, it is therefore now possible to calculate a corresponding family of voltage deviation curves. This family of curves contains all deviations that can possibly occur for this parameter distribution undergoing the given load. We can therefore now ask, whether it is possible to find a set of representative cells, whose voltage deviation curves envelope this family of curves with a certain probability. Finding such a set of *virtual* cells would allow

Fig. 11. Statistical analysis of the obtained parameter variations. **Top Left:** ΔC , ΔR and ΔSoC_{init} with ellipsoidal surface including 80% probability. **Bottom Left:** ΔR and ΔSoC_{init} with elliptical contours for different probabilities. **Top Right:** ΔC and ΔSoC_{init} . **Bottom Right:** ΔC and ΔR .

to calculate envelope voltage curves which contain all voltage curves of a defined percentage of cells possibly occurring for this statistical parameter distribution. In order to find a set of representative cells with their parameters $\Delta SoC_{init,R}$, ΔC_R and ΔR_R for a given probability, four general considerations must be taken into account:

- I. Cells which show the minimum or maximum voltage deviation within a given ellipsoid are always placed on the verge of the ellipsoid.
- II. The number of representative cells n_r necessary to envelop all voltage curves for a given probability is not fixed. Even two representative cells might be sufficient to represent all voltage curves if e.g. their initial SoCs are chosen in an extreme matter.
- III. Envelope curves resulting from a limited number of representative cells might not only enclose voltage curves belonging to the desired probability. The quality of representation refers to how precisely a set of representative cells includes only the voltage curves belonging to the desired probability. Increasing the number of representative cells also enables a higher quality of representation.
- IV. Since the initial parameter distribution is zero-centered ($\bar{\mu} = [0; 0; 0]$), the parameters of the representative cells must also be point-symmetric to the center as long as symmetric probability functions are considered.

According to statement (I) and (II), the first step in finding the representative cells is to decide on the suitable number of representatives. In the following, a set of $n_r = 9 = 2^3 + 1$ cells was chosen. This corresponds to two extrema for every parameter plus a center-cell representing the mean voltage curve. It must once more be stated that choosing the number of representative cells is a multi-objective question (less cells/higher level of simplification versus representation quality), which must be tailored to the needs of the application.

After choosing the number of representatives cells, their parameters must be determined. While the mean cell is intuitively positioned in the center of the distribution ($\bar{x} = [0; 0; 0]$), determining the parameters of the eight remaining cells requires a numerical optimization, which is achieved by a three-step process in the following. Throughout the process, the goal is to minimize Eq. (9), which describes the absolute error between the minimum/maximum voltage deviation of all parameter pairings enclosed by the ellipsoid surface ΔV_S and the minimum/maximum voltage deviation ΔV_R given by the representative cells for the entire range of $\overline{SoC} = 0 \dots 100\%$.

$$\min |(\Delta V_{R,\min/\max}(SoC) - (\Delta V_{S,\min/\max}(SoC)))| \quad \forall \overline{SoC} \quad (9)$$

The following process was conducted for total probabilities of 70, 80, 90 and 95% with the resulting representative cells for 80% being shown in Fig. 11.

Step I: The initial states-of-charge $\Delta SoC_{init,R}$ of the representative cells were set to the minimum and maximum values of the respective ellipsoid surface $\Delta SoC_{init,S}$. Both higher or lower values would inevitably lead to an over- or underestimation of the voltage behavior by the simplified model.

Step II: In order to determine the representative capacity deviations, Eq. (9) was minimized for a load current $I = 0$ with ΔC as a free parameter. Setting the load current to zero is viable, since the voltage change resulting from the capacity deviation is not dependent on the current (see Eq. (7)).

Step III: As for the capacity deviation, the representative resistance deviations ΔR_R were also determined via minimizing Eq. (9) for the entire SoC range. However, this time an actual load current must be considered. Defining this current can be approached from different perspectives. Using the maximum current rating of the system (2.45C i.e. 157 A) guarantees that the simplified model represents the actual profiles during all potential load profiles. However, during phases of lower currents, a significant over-representation must be expected. Alternatively, applying the maximum current of the actual load profile promises the most accurate representation but also requires knowledge about the application. A third option might be suitable for applications where the load distribution is approximately of a Gaussian/Weibull type or follows another defined distribution function. In such cases, values for the standard deviation can be obtained allowing a precise definition, how often the simplified model is able to represent the system. During the following validation, the maximum current of the actual load profile was used.

After introducing the three-step numerical process, it might be of interest, whether an analytical calculation of the representative cells would also be possible. An analytical solution would indeed be possible for models with a relationship between parameter deviations and voltage deviations that can be described analytically. For the applied model, elements such as the look-up of the OCV curves hinder this approach.

5.3. Validation of simplified model

In the first step, the introduced simplification process was validated against synthetic voltage curves. For this purpose, a set of 100 parameter pairings was randomly generated by using the covariance matrix used during the model simplification. By using Eq. (6) it was identified, whether each of these synthetic parameter pairings is placed within the surfaces corresponding to a probability of 70, 80, 90 or 95%. The actual

Fig. 12. Voltage curves of 100 synthetic cells during an excerpt of the validation profile. The envelope curves for a P_S of 80% and 90% are overlaid.

Table 4

Results of the validation of the simplification process. P_A and P_E correspond to the verification against 100 synthetic cells. ϵ_{MAE} relates to the validation against the validation data obtained in Section 4.

P_S	70%	80%	90%	95%
P_A	70%	78%	92%	94%
P_E	74%	84%	94%	96%
ϵ_{MAE}	0.86 mV	1.66 mV	2.89 mV	3.93 mV

percentage P_A of cells lying within those surfaces is given in Table 4. The occurring deviation (e.g. only 78% of parameter pairings can be found within the 80% probability surface) is due to the limited number of pairings.

In the next step, the obtained parameter pairings were used to parameterize a 100s2p model which was subjected to the stationary load profile given in Section 4. Fig. 12 shows the resulting 100 cell voltage curves as gray lines for a section of the profile. In the next step, the stationary load profile was re-simulated with a 9s1p model using the representative parameter pairings obtained during the model simplification. During this simulation, the load profile was scaled down according to the number of parallel cells. The resulting mean and envelope curves for 80 and 90% are also given in Fig. 12. The envelope curves were calculated as the minimum and maximum values of the nine voltage curves given by the 9s1p model. By counting, how many of the gray voltage curves can be found inside the envelope curves for the entire profile, the percentage of enveloped cells P_E can be obtained. Table 4 relates the theoretical probability P_S , the actual number of pairings within the surfaces P_A and the percentage of enveloped voltage curves P_E .

As shown by the results, the envelope curves resulting from the simplified 9s1p model include more cells than expected. Regarding $P_S = 90%$ as an example, the actual contour comprises 92 of the 100 synthetic cells but the envelope curve includes the voltage curves of 94 cells at any given time. As introduced in Section 5.2, this effect of over-representation is due to the limited number of representative points.

In addition to the validation against synthetic voltage curves, the simplified 9s1p model was also validated against the original full-scale system model. The comparison of the voltage spreads calculated from both models is shown in Fig. 13 with the resulting mean absolute error given in Table 4. It can be seen that the simplified model with a P_S of 80, 90 and 95% consistently outputs higher voltage spreads compared

Fig. 13. Comparison of voltage spread curves of the simplified and full-scale system model.

Fig. A.14. Results of impedance determination described in Section 2.3. **Top Left:** Measured voltage profile during pulse tests. **Top Right:** Obtained parameters for R_s . **Center Left:** Obtained parameters for R_{p1} . **Center Right:** Obtained parameters for R_{p2} . **Bottom Left:** Obtained parameters for C_{p1} . **Bottom Right:** Obtained parameters for C_{p2} .

to the full-scale model. Only the 70%-curve is exceeded by the full-scale model after eight hours of profile time (Section 1). While this behavior seems contradictory on first glance, it corresponds directly to the parameterization. Looking at the experimental data points used in the full-scale model (see Fig. 11) it can be seen that only one data point lies significantly outside the 70%-surface, while no data point exceeds the 80%-surface.

6. Conclusions

The experimental methods proposed in this study can be used to determine the capacity and resistance deviation for battery cells in a series topology. Since the procedures can be conducted on the assembled system, the characterization effort can be significantly reduced compared to common single-cell measurements. The acquired data was further used to parameterize a battery system model representing a 14s2p commercial battery module. The validation showed that the resulting model is able to calculate the voltage spread with an mean average error of 1.1 mV for the 24 h stationary load profile. Apart from the well-known influences of capacity and resistance deviations, the variation between the OCV curves of the individual cells has also proven to be of relevance for the model quality.

In order to reduce the computational demands of the model, a statistical simplification process was introduced. The proposed method allowed the determination of representative parameter pairings which were used to parameterize a simplified 9s1p model. During the validation, the simplified model was used to calculate envelope voltage curves, which included 74, 84, 94 and 96% of the family of curves calculated from a virtual 100s2p module. The evident over-representation compared to the desired percentages (70, 78, 92 and 94%) is due to the limited number of representative cells, which must be chosen in the beginning of the simplification process. Applying the simplified model reduced the computational effort from 86.6 to 3.2 s per hour profile time. Apart from the reduction of cells to simulate (28 to nine), this improvement is largely due to the massive reduction of required table look-ups, which makes up for a large share of the computation time.

Applying the proposed tool chain in a stationary application raises additional question, which must be approached in further research. Regarding the characterization, including parallel topologies might be of the essence. At cell level, this will prove difficult, as cell-specific current measurements are not available in commercial battery modules as of now. At system level however, e.g. concerning imbalances between parallel racks, an implementation in the tool chain is conceivable and might also be beneficial in a live digital twin application. In terms of the modeling process, the extension of the model towards further electrical CtCVs but especially thermal and aging aspects might be valuable, e.g. for long-term optimization problems. Concerning the model simplification it can be said that, while already visible on module level, the full benefits only come to play for the large-scale systems consisting of thousands of individual cells to which these methods are tailored. As discussed, the implementation of the initial SoC as a statistical value might be replaced by integrating information available from the systems BMS. Also, the question of the suitable number of representatives might be decided differently for such systems, as the computational effort might still be justifiable while significantly decreasing the over-representation. This trade-off is to be thoroughly investigated in following studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexander Reiter: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Susanne Lehner:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition. **Oliver Bohlen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Dirk Uwe Sauer:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix. Impedance determination results

See Fig. A.14.

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